

DIFFUZ TOKSIK BUQOQ KECHISHIDA D VITAMINING AHAMIYATI

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Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi, Toshkent, O'zbekiston

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7604958>

Tadqiqot maqsadi. Diffuz toksik buqoq (DTB) bilan og'rigan bemorlarda D vitamini darajasini nazorat guruhi uchun olinganlar bilan solishtirish va kasallik kechishida D vitamini darajasini laboratoriya va klinik ko'rsatkichlar bilan bog'lash. Bundan tashqari, D vitamini metabolizmida ishtirok etadigan genlarning genetik o'zgarishini va ularning diffuz toksik buqoq bilan bog'liqligini ko'rib chiqish.

Materiallar va usullar. Toshkent Tibbiyot Akademiyasi 2-klinikasi Endokrinologiya bo'limi, Toshkent Tibbiyot Akademiyasi ko'p tarmoqli klinikasi 2-son Ichki Kasalliklar kafedrasini va Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan endokrinologiya ilmiy-amaliy markazida diffuz toksik buqoq bilan kasallangan bemorlar kuzatuvga olindi (20 nafar) va nazorat guruhidagi 20 nafar bemor ham kuzatuvga olindi, ularda D vitaminining miqdori aniqlab chiqildi. D vitamini darajasi yangi tashxis qo'yilgan diffuz toksik buqoq bilan kasallangan 20 ta bemor va 20 ta nazorat guruhidagilar taqqoslandi. Bemorlarda D vitamini retseptorlari (VDR), vitamin D bog'lovchi oqsil (DBP) va 1-a-gidroksilaza (CYP27B1) dagi yagona nukleotid polimorfizmlari (SNP) ni diffuz toksik buqoq bilan aloqadorligini aniqlash maqsadida tekshirildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari: Diffuz toksik buqoq bilan og'rigan bemorlarni nazorat guruhidagilar bilan solishtirilganda D vitamini darajasi sezilarli darajada past ekanligi aniqlandi ($55,0 \pm 23,2$ va $87,2 \pm 27,6$ nmol / L, $p < 0,001$). Diffuz toksik buqoq bilan kasallangan bemorlarda tashxis qo'yilganda D vitamini darajasi va erkin tiroksin (fT4), erkin triyodotironin (fT3), tirotropin retseptorlari antikorlari (TRAb) o'rtasida bog'liqlik yo'q edi. Bemorlarni antitiroid dorilar bilan davolash, D vitaminining genetik tekshiruvlari, D vitamin retseptorlarining sezuvchanligini aniqlash bilan qalqonsimon bez gormonlari miqdori o'rtasida bog'lanish yo'q edi.

Xulosa. Kuzatuv va tahlillarga ko'ra diffuz toksik buqoq bilan og'rigan bemorlarda D vitamini darajasi tekshiruv uchun olingan nazorat guruhidagilarga nisbatan pastligi aniqlandi. Ammo D vitamini darajasi diffuz toksik buqoq bilan og'rigan bemorlarning laboratoriya yoki klinik ko'rsatkichlariga ta'sir qilmadi. VDRdagi SNPlar D vitamini darajasini pasaytirishi boshqa mexanizmlar orqali diffuz toksik buqoq bilan og'rigan bemorlarga xavfli ta'sir ko'rsatdi.

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